

LEADERSHIP CREATIVITY OF SCHOOL HEADS AND CITIZENSHIP PERFORMANCE OF TEACHER

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2025-2026. Research instruments on leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the study found to exhibit a high level of leadership creativity of school heads. This means that the provisions relating to leadership creativity of school heads is oftentimes observed. The study revealed a high level of citizenship performance of teacher. This indicates that the provisions relating to citizenship performance of teacher are embodied in the item is oftentimes observed. The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher. This implies that the higher the leadership creativity of school heads, the higher is the citizenship performance of teacher. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher was rejected.

Keywords: leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher, school administration and supervision, quantitative research.

I. INTRODUCTION

The citizenship performance of teachers refers to the voluntary, extra-role behaviors that go beyond formal job descriptions, such as helping colleagues, promoting a positive school environment, and contributing to the community and institution. It is also the extent to which educators contribute to the well-being of their school communities, exhibit social responsibility, and actively engage in practices that promote democratic values, respect, and fairness. This is crucial to the overall functioning and success of schools (Ali, Siddique, Siddique, Abbas & Ali, 2021).

However, a significant problem arises when teachers fail to demonstrate adequate citizenship performance, which can have negative consequences on the school environment, student development, and the broader community. In Malaysia, a study involving 824 secondary school teachers found that the overall level of citizenship performance of teachers among Malaysian teachers was moderate, not high. This suggests that extra-role behaviors, such as helping colleagues, participating in school activities beyond one's formal duties, or advocating for the school, are not strongly embedded in routine teacher practice (Choong, Ng, Ai Na & Tan, 2020).

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One of the central challenges to improving citizenship performance among teachers is the increasing workload and administrative demands that many educators face. Surveys reveal Filipino teachers work an average of 52 hours per week, with one in four exceeding 60 hours. This far exceeds the statutory maximum of 40 hours per week, comprising 6 hours of teaching and 2 hours for teaching-related tasks as stipulated by the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers. This situation made teachers overwhelmed with administrative tasks, documentation, and multiple roles, they have less time, energy, and motivation to engage in behaviors like helping colleagues, mentoring students outside class, and volunteering in school events (Cabaluna & Moleta Jr, 2023).

In the local setting, like any other teachers in the country or the region, teachers in Davao Occidental Division have also concerns on citizenship performance. This is due to the fact that they have high share of non-teaching duties. In fact, around 55% of teachers' time (approximately 28.6 hours per week) is spent on administrative and ancillary responsibilities, not on classroom instruction. Teachers handle an average of five additional roles, such as coordinating programs, advising groups, and administrative functions, particularly burdensome in small schools, making them feel tired to perform any other tasks.

This study seeks to underscore the relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher to ascertain the relationship between the two variables. Today, the researcher has rarely come across with a study on the study regarding these two variables. It is in this context that the researcher prompted to conduct this study to address contextual gap.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study is aimed to find out the relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. What is the level of leadership creativity of school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1 Personality;
 - 1.2 Individual Creativity;
 - 1.3 Organizational Creativity;
 - 1.4 Organizational Leadership, and
 - 1.5 Team Creativity?
2. What is the level of citizenship performance of teacher in terms of:
 - 2.1 Initiative;
 - 2.2 Adaptability;
 - 2.3 Dependability, and
 - 2.4 Cooperation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher?

Hypothesis

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational technique. Non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing a correlational technique is a type of research approach used to examine the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. It falls under quantitative research because it involves collecting and analyzing numerical data. The term non-experimental indicates that the researcher does not control or manipulate any variables, unlike in experimental research, where treatments or interventions are applied.

Non-experimental correlational research is a research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables, without establishing cause and effect in which in this study, it will look into the relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This will be used to determine the level of leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher.

Pearson r. This will be used to determine the significance of the relationship between task leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Leadership Creativity of School Heads

Shown in Table 1 is the level of leadership creativity of school heads with an overall mean of 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent of high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study. Among the enumerated indicators, organizational leadership has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.18 or high, personality, 4.15 or high, organizational creativity, 4.14 or high, team creativity, 4.15 or high, and individual creativity, 4.10 or high.

Table 1. Leadership Creativity of School Heads

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Personality	4.15	High
Individual Creativity	4.10	High
Organizational Creativity	4.14	High
Organizational Leadership	4.18	High
Team Creativity	4.13	High
Overall	4.14	High

The result of the study corresponds with the statement of Szempruch, Potyrała, Smyła & Tomczyk (2024) who reported that Leadership creativity of school heads plays a vital role in shaping an innovative and productive learning environment. Creative school leaders are able to think beyond traditional administrative practices and introduce new strategies that enhance teaching and learning. They encourage teachers to explore different instructional methods, integrate technology into classrooms, and design programs that address the diverse needs of students.

The result of the study is consistent with the statement of Beresford-Dey, Ingram & Lakin (2022) who noted that creative leadership helps school heads effectively manage problems and opportunities within the school community. When faced with limited resources, changing policies, or diverse student populations, creative leaders find practical and innovative solutions. They may develop partnerships with the community, organize collaborative projects among teachers, or implement new systems that improve communication and efficiency. Through these initiatives, school heads demonstrate flexibility and strategic thinking, which helps the school remain responsive to changing educational demands.

The result of the study supports the statement of Pangestu & Karwan (2021) who declared that leadership creativity fosters a culture of collaboration, motivation, and continuous improvement among teachers and students. School heads who model creativity encourage their staff to share ideas, experiment with new teaching practices, and participate in professional development activities. This supportive environment builds trust and teamwork within the school. As a result, both teachers and students become more engaged, and the overall quality of education improves. Creative leadership therefore serves as a powerful tool for guiding schools toward innovation and long-term success.

Level of Citizenship Performance of Teacher

Shown in Table 2 is the level of citizenship performance of teacher with an overall mean of 4.11 with a descriptive equivalent of high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Table 2. Citizenship Performance of Teacher

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Initiative	4.11	High
Adaptability	4.12	High
Dependability	4.09	High
Cooperation	4.13	High
Overall	4.11	High

Among the enumerated indicators, cooperation has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.13 or high, adaptability, 4.12 or high, initiative 4.11 or high, and dependability, 4.09 or high.

The result of the study supports the statement of Ali, Siddique, Siddique, Abbas & Ali (2021) who affirms that Citizenship performance of teachers refers to the voluntary behaviors and actions that teachers demonstrate beyond their formal job responsibilities to support the school, students, and colleagues. These behaviors are not usually included in official job descriptions but contribute significantly to the overall effectiveness and positive climate of the school. Teachers who display strong citizenship performance willingly assist their peers, participate in school activities, and contribute to the improvement of the school community. Their commitment and dedication help create a supportive and collaborative environment that enhances both teaching and learning.

The result of the study is in agreement with the statement of Fauziah, Hali & Jaya (2025) who asserts that one important aspect of teachers' citizenship performance is their willingness to cooperate and collaborate with colleagues. Teachers who exhibit this quality often share instructional materials, provide guidance to new teachers, and participate actively in team discussions and school initiatives. They also show respect, professionalism, and concern for the welfare of others within the school.

The result of the study reflects the statement of Hermanto & Srimulyani (2022) who acknowledges that citizenship performance involves teachers' active participation in activities that contribute to the success of the school as a whole. This may include volunteering for committees, organizing extracurricular activities, mentoring students, and supporting school programs and policies. Teachers who demonstrate strong citizenship performance help build a positive school culture and serve as role models for students.

Significance on the Relationship between Leadership Creativity of School Heads and Citizenship Performance of Teacher

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.623 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher is rejected.

The result of the study corroborates the statement of Çevik (2025) who supports the claim that The significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and the citizenship performance of teachers highlights how effective and innovative leadership directly influences the behaviors and attitudes of teaching staff. School heads who demonstrate creativity in their leadership inspire teachers to go beyond their formal duties and actively contribute to the school community. When leaders model innovative problem-solving, flexibility, and visionary thinking, teachers are more likely to exhibit citizenship behaviors such as cooperation, initiative, adaptability, and dependability. This relationship indicates that a creative leadership style not only drives organizational improvement but also fosters a positive, collaborative, and proactive school culture.

Table 3. Significance on the Relationship between Leadership Creativity of School Heads and Citizenship Performance of Teacher

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Leadership Creativity of School Heads and Citizenship Performance of Teacher	0.623	0.000	Reject

The result of the study reinforces the statement of Ahmed (2025) who establishes that research has shown that the more creative a school head is in organizing, motivating, and guiding the school, the higher the level of voluntary and constructive behaviors displayed by teachers. Teachers are more engaged, willing to collaborate with colleagues, and motivated to participate in school initiatives when their leaders encourage innovative thinking and value contributions beyond routine responsibilities.

The result of the study resonates with the statement of Ertürk (2023) who demonstrates that the significant relationship emphasizes that leadership creativity and teachers' citizenship performance are mutually reinforcing. Creative leaders who encourage experimentation and recognize teachers' efforts contribute to a supportive environment where teachers feel empowered to take initiative and adapt to changing needs. This not only improves teacher performance but also strengthens the overall effectiveness and sustainability of school programs. In essence, the presence of creative leadership enhances teachers' citizenship behaviors, which in turn supports continuous growth, innovation, and a thriving educational environment.

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a high level of leadership creativity of school heads. This means that the provisions relating to leadership creativity of school heads is oftentimes observed. The study revealed a high level of citizenship performance of teacher. This indicates that the provisions relating to citizenship performance of teacher are embodied in the item is oftentimes observed. The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher. This implies that the higher the leadership creativity of school heads, the higher is the citizenship performance of teacher. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher was rejected.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study found to exhibit a high level of leadership creativity of school heads. The researcher recommends that they may improve in the area of individual creativity as this obtained the lowest mean score among all the indicators. The principals may leverage teachers' personality traits to foster creativity by recognizing and appreciate the unique personality traits of each teacher, such as self-esteem, respect for others' opinions, and social tendencies (extrovert/introvert); encourage collaborative feedback and peer engagement by promoting a culture where teachers' opinions are valued by facilitating regular team discussions, peer reviews, and collaborative brainstorming sessions; support problem-solving and initiative by encouraging teachers to develop and implement innovative ideas to solve classroom or school challenges; promote a positive outlook on challenges by training and modeling strategies that help teachers view problems, complaints, and bottlenecks as opportunities for improvement rather than obstacles, and reduce routine barriers to creativity by identifying and streamlining repetitive or administrative tasks that may limit teachers' time for creative thinking.

The study revealed a high level of citizenship performance of teacher. The researcher recommends that the teachers may improve in the area of dependability as this is the lowest among all the indicators. The teachers may maintain and strengthen attendance compliance by continuing to adhere consistently to the school's attendance rules; follow regulations and procedures by applying regulations consistently in daily tasks, classroom management, and interactions with students and staff; demonstrate responsibility and accountability by taking ownership of assigned tasks, ensuring they are completed thoroughly and on time; exhibit personal discipline in work by organizing daily tasks and plan your workload to ensure efficiency and quality of work, and work reliably without supervision by taking initiative in completing tasks without requiring constant oversight.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between leadership creativity of school heads and citizenship performance of teacher. The researchers recommend that teachers may embrace creative leadership by engaging actively in collaborative problem-solving, taking advantage of the creative environment provided by leadership; enhance citizenship behaviors by approaching challenges with a proactive mindset, viewing problems as opportunities to contribute meaningfully, and provide constructive feedback by sharing ideas and suggestions with school heads to support continuous improvement and creative problem-solving.

School principals may foster a creative work environment by encouraging teachers to experiment with new ideas and teaching methods; promote teacher citizenship by recognizing and reward teachers who demonstrate initiative, cooperation, adaptability, and reliability; model creative leadership by demonstrating flexible thinking, openness to new ideas, and innovative approaches to challenges.

District supervisors may support school-level creative leadership by providing training and workshops for principals on creative leadership strategies; promote collaboration between schools by facilitating sharing of best practices and innovative programs among schools, and assess and recognize impact by developing evaluation systems that measure both leadership creativity and teacher citizenship performance.

The researcher also recommends to future researchers to conduct similar study and explore some indicators that are not included in this study in another setting in order to uncover new knowledge relevant to the topics presented in this study.

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